

**INVESTIGATING NATIONAL HARMONY IN TEXT AND CONTEXT OF
SELECTED NIGERIAN UNIVERSITY MOTTOS**

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Abstract

Pragmatics as a field of language study seeks to bring out reality as dictated by numerous intentions and conditions of physical, linguistic, political, social, behavioural, cultural and situational contexts. Pragmatics as a context-of-utterance-based field is interested in what speakers/writers do and why they do it whenever they speak/write - what made Mey (1994) and (2001) refer to this field as 'the total human *context of use*'. This study seeks to reveal the 'invisible' meanings embedded in different Nigerian university mottos by their pragmatic felicities for national harmony. Data for the study were obtained from the websites of each of the twelve (12) universities represented with the use of a stratified random sampling technique for data selection; thus, our data cuts across federal, state and private (both secular and faith-based) universities. It was discovered that many Nigerian universities still hinge on using Latin mottos due to their deep historical affiliation to university learning and richness in witty linguistic constructions. Another discovery showed that both the linguistic and psychological context of most of the universities maintain educational harmony through the use of either 'knowledge' or 'learning' in their mottos. On a final note, what makes both staff and students of any academic institution goal-driven is summarised in mottos; and for its credence to be well brought to the fore, all the stakeholders concerned should be well aligned with the mottos' pragmatic contexts to attain national harmony, which is one of core factors for establishing academic institutions.

Keywords: motto, pragmatics, pragmatic context, language use

Introduction

Maintenance of harmony rests on proper locations for proper occasions which arise via diverse textual forms. It could either be performative or constative based on Austin's (1975) two broad methods of getting things done. Out of the methods comes text which could be as short as a single letter or as long as prose and drama pieces. However, context is what influences a text. This is why Spencer-Oatey and Zegarac (2002: 74-91) propose that:

Pragmatics is concerned with the study of the meaning that linguistic expressions receive in use. So, one task of pragmatics is to explain how

participants.... move from the de-contextualized (that is, linguistically encoded) meanings of the words and phrases to grasp of their meaning in context.”

Communication (pragmatics) cannot exist in a vacuum; it is an elaborative process through which speakers or writers and listeners or readers construct meaning which proves the result of the combination of both text and context. Even though context harbours both world knowledge and socio-cultural ability to aid meaning construction, the text is used to codify human thought. Therefore, they both go together in the construction of university mottos. This is because a university is a mini-world of divergent forms of experiences and educational policy formulations. It is a universe of learning and knowledge where disciplines and series of educational interests are taught, learned and developed for tangible implementation across the world. Hence, the philosophy and goals of each institution are injected behind the formation of their mottos.

It is the above-stated basis that spurs the interest of these researchers in weighing the level of harmonious relationship existing in the formation of diverse Nigerian university mottos and their manifestations in their immediate geographical habitats. Significantly, this work is vested in the belief that both educated and uneducated Nigerians have their uncompromising proportion to receive from each university on how to live harmonious, resourceful and fulfilling lives; divergent philosophies of each of the different universities can shape and facilitate harmonious living among people of dissimilar philosophical, religious, ethical and educational backgrounds.

Methodology for the Study

This study covers four regional parts of Nigeria namely; the northern, the southern, the eastern and the western parts of Nigeria. Data selection was based on a stratified random sampling technique to select three sets of data comprising the federal universities, state universities and private universities in each of the aforesaid regions into each stratum for analysis. It is, hence, expected that the data for analysis total up to twelve mottos of different Nigerian universities.

Scope of the Study

This study borders much on three (linguistic, psychological and socio-cultural contexts) out of the four common types of pragmatic context. Analysis of physical context shall be left out of our analysis because the location descriptions of each motto of the universities covered suffice for their physical representation.

Theoretical Framework

This work is aimed at dissecting how text and the pragmatic context in selected Nigerian university mottos appeal for national harmony and represent an instrument of unity behind educational pursuits. Out of numerous scholastic explanations given to the study of language, this work favours Jacob L. Mey’s argument that simply divides the tasks involved in the study of language into two: a description of its structure as dealt with by the traditional method of grammar, and a description of its use to be taken care of

by pragmatics (Mey, 2001:5). In essence, this research shall survey the process of production of university mottos by considering the relation of signs (words hinged together to form each symbolic motto) to us, the interpreters, (Morris, 1938:6) before it unravels the common orienting feature for each university's 'point of view' as reflective from their diverse context of language use.

Literature Review

Text

Text is something that happens, in the form of talking or writing, listening or reading. When we analyse it, we analyse the product of this process; and the term 'text' is usually taken as referring to the product – especially the product in its written form, since this is most clearly perceptible as an object, though since that we have had tape recorders it has become easier for people to conceive of spoken language also as text (Halliday and Matthiessen, 2014:593).

Hinging on the two intermediate patterns that are further highlighted by Halliday and Matthiessen (2014:593), "the system of a language is instantiated as text, the two representing the poles at either end of the clime of instantiation", describing the functions of text becomes necessary. The two main functions of text (discourse) as read from Butt, Fahey, Spinks and Yallop (1995:5), Yule (2006:114), Halliday and Matthiessen (2014:593) and Jackson and Stockwell (2011:25), are for '*interactional*' and '*transactional purposes*'. Interactional texts are used to build relationships between people while transactional texts function as vehicles for conveying some information or getting something done; they dwell much on the content of what is said or written.

Moreover, some scholars even believe that text is language. Hence, due to the pragmatic perspective of looking at the meaning of the text, we can say it is "the language in use" which portrays the definition of pragmatics by Yule (2006:114). It is likewise based on viewing the text as a language that Bloor and Bloor (2004:17) propose that "a text has texture". They further describe the texture as "the quality of being a text, rather than a set of unconnected bits of language textbook".

It can thus be said that text is the language we use to talk about what we use to 'reform', 'inform', 'perform' and 'deform' based on Adedimeji's (2006:181-194) notion of non-verbal pragmatics. Though, all the aforementioned doings are linked (when necessary) with cohesive devices to ensure their metafunctional capacity such as textual, interpersonal and ideational linguistic metafunctions.

Types of Text

To start with, the two main methods of getting things done are through 'performative' and 'constative' acts as declared by Austin (1975). There is no doubt that acts can simply be derived from texts, either spoken or written. Therefore, these two shall be firstly considered as text types among others. On performative acts, Austin claims that it is used in a variety of cognate ways and constructions, much as the term 'imperative'. On the other hand, he holds that not all true or false statements are descriptions, and for this reason, he prefers to use the word 'constative' (Austin, 1975:6-11).

Nevertheless, the dominant properties of text or what characterizes its structure can suggest the type to be given to a text. The text type is viewed as a genre of texts in the sense that novels usually exhibit all text types. Novels may be narrative, descriptive, expository, persuasive, or instructional; all of which can also be found in short stories. The above description can be simply summarized with Jackson and Stockwell's (2011:26) position thus:

We will divide the functions of discourses and texts into five broad categories: telling a story (narrative), describing someone, or something (descriptive), explaining a concept (expository) convincing someone of an opinion, or getting them to do something (persuasive) telling someone how to do something (instructive).

We can then say that the text typologies include a limited number of different items; hence we aim at a complete set of possible types that can make up any text. Therefore, subcategories of historical and literary genres like sonnet, recipe, homepage et cetera are not considered in this typology.

Context

Adedimeji, a professor of pragmatics, is known for a statement: “Don’t talk of the text, talk of the context”. The fact that ‘context’ is much more emphasized gives us the pragmatic meaning that context is an integral property or tool in pragmatic analysis. The issue of context cannot be overemphasized in language because almost all human deeds and speeches are influenced by one or two forms of context. For instance, it would be ludicrous for a person to shout “ye!!!” without being triggered by anything; the only set of humans that can yell in such a way without any meaningful cause are the lunatics. Based on this, Butt, Fahey, Spinks and Yallop (1995:205) think that:

A speaker/language user gets aware of different and changeable situations around him. It is through this that he discriminates and adjusts, with his accumulated experiences, to different situations of language use. Hence, he will be able to deduce the context of the language we hear or read, and can classify it quite finely, distinguishing for instance, between a general warning, a mild reprimand or a serious chastisement.

Contextual Theory

Firth (1957) cited in Odebunmi (2006) makes his contribution to the theory of context by building on Malnowski’s view in proposing the following categories of context of situation:

- (a) The verbal features of participants
 - The verbal action of the participants
 - The non - verbal action of the participants
- (b) The relevant objects
- (c) The effects of the verbal actions

Context of the situation covers everything going on in the world outside the text but which makes the text what it is. It concerns the extra-linguistic features of a text that

are given substance in the words and grammatical patterns which speakers and writers use consciously or subconsciously to construct texts of different varieties, and which their audience uses to classify and interpret (Butt, Fahey, Spinks and Yallop, 1995).

Features of Context

Hymes (1964) offers more contributions to the features of context. As reported in Osisanwo (2008) and Odebunmi (2006), the features are the following;

- Participants: involve a speaker (or a writer) and a hearer (or a reader);
- Topic: subject of discussion;
- Setting: involves place, time, gesture and posture;
- Channel: what medium is being employed? Is it by speech, writing or sign?
- Code: has to do with language, dialect or language style being used in speech event;
- Message: is it chat, debate, sermon, storytelling etc?
- Event: the nature of the event. For instance, weddings;
- Key: deals with the message form (good or bad);
- Purpose: the participants' expectation of the result of the communicative event.

Types of Context

Generally, scholars have identified four main types of context. They are:

- i. **Physical context:** involves “participants’ (their status, sex, age, occupation and ideology) “activities”, “place” and “time” of a discourse (Osisanwo, 2008).
- ii. **Linguistic context:** deals with how meaning can be generated within the frame of text. Odebunmi (2006) submits that “meaning of a lexical item can be determined by knowing the meaning of the lexical items that surround it”.
- iii. **Psychological context:** has to do with the speaker’s mental stage e.g. cursing someone who did one a great favor can be interpreted as an instance of enthusiasm.
- iv. **Socio-cultural context:** concerns with the social, cultural, religious and historical perspectives of a word or an utterance. Odebunmi (2006) also refers to this as “social context”.

On M.A.K. Hilladay’s perspective about context, the three elements: field, tenor and mode are out of his postulations as he argues that those three tools/factors make up a context in his term – ‘register’. Jackson and Stockwell (2011:25) summarize the register as follows:

Register features are considered under three headings: field, tenor and mode. Field relates to the content or subject matter of text or discourse; tenor relates to the persons who produce and consume a text or discourse and their relationship, mode relates to how a discourse or text is produced and delivered.

Considering how context is conceptualized in three senses by Halliday, it is worth emphasizing that context is a phenomenon on which the interpretation of any utterance, sign and gesture depends. As noted in Odebunmi (2006), Malinowski (1923)

introduced the term “context of situation”. Malinowski used the term to assert the fact that “meaning” is provided only in the context in which the word is uttered.

Meaning of Mottos and Their Functions

The New International Webster’s Comprehensive Dictionary of English Language (2013) describes a motto as “an expressive word or pithy sentence enunciating some guiding principle, rule of conduct, or the like; a phrase inscribed on something or prefixed to literary composition as somehow indicative of its qualities”. The origin of the motto is possibly derived from the Latin *mutterio/ire* – to mutter or mumble; although its manifestation as a verbal encouragement probably goes back to the Greek *paean*. This was originally a song of praise delivered in honour of the god Apollo but became the name used for a song or chant to triumph shouted by victorious troops on the battlefield. Later still, such words or phrases began to be employed in a non-military sphere such as guilds of merchants or artisans. The retention of the motto in the modern era is ubiquitous, but its history is especially to Latin, the universal language of the Mediterranean World and beyond.

Mottos are described to encourage further or enhance achievement in some endeavour or an inspirational ideal. This is why most schools, institutions, companies, professions, charitable and government departments, sporting bodies and clubs in almost all parts of the globe employ the motto as evidence of their mission and vision. Many university mottos that were coined from Latin are now being translated into English as declared by Oduşina (2023) thus: “...many universities have now translated their Latin mottos into English so as to enable people of this age to understand what it means, as the language has almost gone into extinction.”

A further connection of the motto may be identified with the literary genre - the epigram. Mottos are invariably composed to be seen and read while the epigram, again a particular Latin phenomenon, was a short verse often no more than two lines containing pertinent information about a message. The modern motto is invariably contained in a single phrase of rarely more than four to five words. Furthermore, the motto is almost always not in sentence form, often lacking what might appear to be essential syntactic points, so the sense of the message has to be teased out through implication rather than explicit language usage (Evans, 2015).

Analysis of Text and Context of Selected University Mottos

Analysis of selected data will focus on the linguistic, socio-cultural and psychological types of contexts since the work dwells much on selected written texts.

Datum One

University of Abuja, Abuja, FCT

Motto: *“For Unity and Scholarship”*

- a. **Linguistic context:** If we carefully quote the words: ‘unity’ and ‘scholarship’, the above motto establishes the felicity for national harmony and signifies the context of education, for the two words are registers of peaceful co-existence and academic settings.

- b. **Socio-cultural context:** It is a common belief that ‘no one is an island of knowledge’, hence ‘scholarship’ is needed for the smooth-running of the Capital territory of Nigeria. It is also a general socio-cultural belief in Nigeria that ‘a tree cannot make a forest’, therefore, ‘unity’ and convergence of efforts on the university founded in the nation’s central hub (FCT) is the key to maintaining harmonious living amidst diversity in ethnicity, cultural heritages and religions.
- c. **Psychological context:** This motto serves as a clarion call to all and sundry on the purpose of establishing the university in FCT. The indicative locution ‘for’ solidifies the two main undisputable reasons behind the founding of the university; all staff and students and the public are thus required to be strong advocates of unity and scholarship as summarized in the motto.

Datum Two

University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Kwara State

Motto: *‘Probitas Doctrina’* meaning *‘Learning and Character’*

- a. **Linguistic context:** It is mainly the word ‘learning’ that puts this motto in the context of education. Whether it is a formal or informal form of learning is not indicated.
- b. **Socio-cultural context:** The majority of the people of Ilorin believe that whatever levels of knowledge a person possesses, even if it is more than that of satan, without possession of character, the knowledge is a waste. Here, the character refers to the positive aspects of human behaviour like being God-fearing, empathetic, and morally disciplined among others. It is this same ideology that transpires into the mode of functionality of the University of Ilorin.
- c. **Psychological context:** The fact that character comes first in the motto contains a lot of messages such as ‘any would-be student of this university must be disciplined in all ramifications’; ‘the first and foremost quality expected of this university students is *character*’ or ‘the goal of this university is to make student figures of good manner before learning takes place’. This allows us to infer that adults must be disciplined before they acquire knowledge.

Datum Three

Al-Qalam University, Katsina, Katsina State

Motto: *‘Learning for Wisdom and Morality’*

- a. **Linguistic context:** The main word that places the above motto in the context of formal education is ‘learning’. The meaningfulness of learning/acquiring knowledge before any other thing fixes it firmly in the realm of education while the last word – ‘morality’ projects faith.
- b. **Social-cultural context:** The implication of the use of the word- ‘for’ is that ‘wisdom’ and ‘morality’ can be acquired through learning. We can then infer that Al-Qalam University as one of the faith-based private universities in Nigeria believes that learning is for two cardinal reasons in life, and those things are wisdom and morality which makes humans to be religiously upright.
- c. **Psychological context:** Psychologically, it can be inferred from the linguistic context of the motto that, this university wants to make sure by the time the

students graduate, they would have been equipped with much more wisdom and morality, even if they had none before being admitted into the university. The tools equip them to be adherents to God.

Datum Four

University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Oyo State

Motto: *'Recte Sapere Fons'* meaning *'For Knowledge and Sound Judgment'*

- a. **Linguistic context:** The word 'sound judgment' which can mean 'critical thinking' or 'philosophizing' can be linked to various educational disciplines identifiable in the university. The embedded meaning here is that the knowledge gained from this school proves positive in assisting any alumni of the University to contribute to national development.
- b. **Socio-cultural context:** Being the first university in Nigeria, it was a social duty of the University of Ibadan to seek a way of uplifting the students of the University. This testifies to the fact that it is not only for the sake of knowledge and enlightenment that the university was founded but also for the sake of creating bodies that can work with cooperative synergy in the course of national building.
- c. **Psychological context:** The motto of this university communicates to both students and teachers that great minds of sound judgment are produced by the University of Ibadan.

Datum Five

Osun State University, Osogbo, Osun State

Motto: *'30 80'*

- a. **Linguistic context:** The numeral '3080' simply refers to the position of the University. '30' signifies that it is the number thirtieth (30th) State University established in Nigeria while '80' refers to its general position by establishment among all universities in Nigeria.
- b. **Socio-cultural context:** Using numerals to make up a university motto is not at all common in Nigeria. Although, the numerals function the way letters would have, the invisible meaning that could be understood through the numerals is that the science of calculation like mathematics, Physics and Statistics are treated with honour in the university.
- c. **Psychological context:** This motto psychologically begs questions from any new visitor to the university on what informs the choice of the four-figured numbers as their motto.

Datum Six

Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti, Ekiti State

Motto: *'Knowledge, Honour, Service'*

- a. **Linguistic context:** The use of the word 'knowledge' indicates that the motto could be linked to the educational environment. Seeing it first lays more emphasis on its importance.

- b. **Socio-cultural context:** The conventional climax of human achievement is portrayed in the motto. It is the opinion of the founder of the university that education comes first; it is the source through which a man is honored while whatever knowledge acquired is meant for national service.
- c. **Psychological context:** The institution's motto lacks any form of cohesive devices and so, it is asyndetic. This shows the uninterrupted belief of the University that any candidate, existing and new should bear in mind that the three elements of the school motto should be equally treated, for all of them are what a completely learned person has to possess.

Datum Seven

University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Enugu State

Motto: *'To Restore the Dignity of Man'*

- a. **Linguistic context:** The use of the word 'restore' means to return the honor that has eluded the people of Nigeria at large. Its use signifies Nigeria's willingness for education.
- b. **Socio-cultural context:** What could have motivated this are two things: the fact that this university was the first full-fledged indigenous university opened after the Nigerian independence in 1960. The second reason is that from that time, following the American system of education was no more a thing of force but of will.
- c. **Psychological context:** The motto of the university is mainly built upon expressing the freedom of Nigeria and her independence from the Western force of colonial masters. This was coincidentally attained with the formal opening of the University of Nigeria.

Datum Eight

Madonna University, Okija, Anambra State

Motto: *'Sapientia Densursum'* meaning *'Wisdom from Above'*

- a. **Linguistic context:** Underlining the word- 'wisdom' puts this motto in the context of religion which can be noticed through the use of 'above' to complete the godly gift of knowledge.
- b. **Socio-cultural context:** The fact that this is a private Christian university leaves the room for heavenly or godly use of the motto. The University believes that humans gain wisdom from Heaven and not just by their wish or power.
- c. **Psychological context:** A strict attachment that Christians give to the ascendancy of Jesus Christ plays a major role here. Thus, it could be inferred that teachers and students of the University are implored by the motto to seek heavenly wisdom which they believe Jesus Christ intervenes to deliver.

Datum Nine

Caritas University, Amoriji-Nike, Enugu State

Motto: *'Love for Education and Morals'*

- a. **Linguistic context:** The use of the word 'education' clearly tells the reader that the context is meant for learning. Higher importance is placed on education in the motto to ascertain its necessity before 'moral' could be used to earn human love.
- b. **Social-cultural context:** Being a Christian school means there is a high demand for the moral upbringing of students and even moral instillation in the workers of the school. Therefore, the University holds in mind that by the time a student or worker leaves the university premises daily, he/she will have developed a love for education and morals.
- c. **Psychological context:** The University could be said to have the belief that, loving two things –'education' and 'morals' is the hallmark of a dignified person in society.

Datum Ten

Niger-Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State

Motto: *'Creativity, Excellence and Service'*

- a. **Linguistic context:** The use of the first word 'creativity' indicates the university is ready to achieve excellence in their students through creativity and prepare the non-creative ones to be.
- b. **Social-cultural context:** The world-knowledge attached to this motto is that the university does not only offer the theoretical aspect of learning but also the practical aspect which invariably leads to academic 'excellence' and in turn useful for both the individual and the national 'service'. It suggests that Bayelsa State is socially creative in culture.
- c. **Psychological context:** We can infer from the motto that attaining knowledge from a creative point of view is considered the best option by this university and that is why it comes first over and above the other words 'excellence' and 'service'.

Datum Eleven

University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State

Motto: *'Knowledge for Service'*

- a. **Linguistic context:** Putting the word 'knowledge' first communicates the importance of learning in this context. It delimits our thinking in an educational setting.
- b. **Socio-cultural context:** Priority is given to education through the word 'knowledge'. It is expected that her would-be students have a limitless desire to achieve their goals and be impactful to society through the knowledge garnered from the University for public 'service'.
- c. **Psychological context:** It is deductible from the motto that, it is when knowledge is acquired that a person can render any meaningful service to the immediate society.

Datum Twelve

University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River State

Motto: *‘Knowledge for Service’*

- a. **Linguistic context:** Being grounded in the pursuit of knowledge for enlightenment is communicated with the word ‘knowledge’, making education the hub of the establishment.
- b. **Socio-cultural context:** Serving the nation is sacrosanct in the tradition of this university. Maintaining a helping culture and usefulness to the world with experiences garnered from the university to ‘serve’ the public is of utmost importance to the sustainability of her principle.
- c. **Psychological context:** The deep-lying ideology within this university motto suggests that the driving force behind acquiring any form of knowledge should be national and public service.

Summary of Implications of Linguistic Context on Socio-cultural and Psychological Interpretations

Academism: Scholarship/learning/education/knowledge = 8 (34.8%)

Patriotism: Service = 4 (17.4%)

Responsibility: Unity/character/sound judgment/honour/dignity/love/excellence = 7 (30.4%)

Religiousness: Wisdom/moral(ity)/above = 4 (17.4%)

Figure 1: Summary of Implications of Linguistic Context on interpretations

Findings

Some level of commonness and unity was discovered among the eastern and the southern Nigerian universities through much use of the word ‘service’. This is to emphasize their pragmatic and cultural attachment to the word; and it occurs to the extent that two of the Universities – the University of Benin and the University of Calabar use the same motto: *‘Knowledge for service’*.

It was found that some Nigerian universities hold on to the view of using the Latin language (due to its richness in witty and emotional linguistic history) in constructing their mottos. Some of the Universities in this category are the University of Ibadan and the University of Ilorin among some other numerous unmentioned universities, including state and private ones. This gives homage to formal and higher education which derives its root from the era of Latin as the language of instruction.

Also, the tradition of using only speech letters in motto-making is no longer the only existing system. Using numerals and figures meant for mathematical purposes has been considered by one university (Osun State University) as the best medium through which its intention could be conveyed. This unifies the goal of all universities to be science and mathematical-oriented in the 21st century.

Nevertheless, it is only in the northern part of Nigeria that private Islamic universities are found with common goals; even two of the universities, Al-Qalam University, Kastina and Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin (not in our data due to limited space) use the same motto: *'learning for wisdom and morality'*.

Another instance of commonness applies to the universities across the four regions as discipline is much more emphasized. For instance, the University of Ilorin's 'probitas' means character which stands for 'being disciplined'; Al-Qalam University, Katsina and Caritas University use 'morality' to foreground the demand for being disciplined at all costs; the University of Ibadan's 'sound judgment' and the University of Nigeria's 'dignity' is to invoke an unwavering sense of thorough discipline.

It was also established from the percentage of the pragmatic implicature of the texts across all the mottos considered that unity of thought in pursuance of academism and fulfillment of communal responsibility towards the nation superimposes all other things. This is proven by eight (8) words representing 34.8% and seven (7) words representing 30.4% as contained in the summary chart for implication of linguistic context on the general contextual analysis.

Finally, the motto of the University located in Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria, revealed a general socio-cultural belief of the nation that a tree cannot make a forest; therefore, 'unity' and convergence of efforts on the university in the nation's central hub (FCT) is the key to maintain harmonious living amidst diversity in ethnicity, cultural heritages and religions.

Recommendations

Based on the foregoing, it is recommended that the linguistic interface between the mottos of Colleges of Education, Polytechnics, and Monotechnics should also be studied to delineate the big role to be played by Nigerian higher institutions of learning in driving the nation towards unwavering harmony. Nonetheless, it is recommended that each higher institution of learning, federal, state, or private, drive towards the same goal of making their students agents of positive thought and peaceful co-existence through the inherent messages of their mottos right from their day in school.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has revealed that meanings and their contextual properties can be encoded in different forms, some of which are through letters, numbers and theology. This is shown in the data for this work where mottos are represented with different kinds of language and different ideologies to communicate the decision, mission and vision of different universities in Nigeria. Though different contextual backgrounds led to the use of different mottos, the expression of the universities' goal-driven philosophies establishes a powerful harmonious motif behind their establishment which in turn aids national harmony.

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